

Concept of the RDMTraining4NFDI Hybrid Event on Research Data Management for NFDI Consortia

28 October – 11 December 2025

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1. Introduction

Context

The RDMTraining4NFDI Hybrid Event on Research Data Management (RDM) for National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) Consortia was organised as part of the Base4NFDI project RDMTraining4NFDI to complete Work Package 2 (WP2), 'Training format development'.

The aim of WP2 was to set up RDM training events for RDM trainers and subsequently evaluate them in terms of content and formats. The aim was also to assist consortia in creating training materials with general core content and data-specific adaptations. The overarching goal was to coordinate RDM training within the German RDM community, and more specifically within the NFDI.

Positioning of the Event

The workflow for creating and delivering the Hybrid Event (as set out in this document and other published materials linked to the event) is a technical-organisational solution that meets both the Base4NFDI basic service definition and the goals of RDMTraining4NFDI. Additionally, we provided through this event support to consortia to carry out discipline-specific adaptations.

During the event, materials from the training materials collection delivered for Work Package 1, 'Content blueprint', were reused and adapted, such as the following:

- Online Training Workshop (slides) on Research Data Management in (Bio-)Medicine: <https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006452660>
- Workshop (slides) on Data Sharing and Publishing: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16792999>

Purpose of the Training Event

The purpose of the Hybrid Event was as follow:

- Provide practical, focused RDM guidance within a condensed timeframe.
- Strengthen participants' training skills and expertise in data management.
- Encourage the adaptation of RDM training to different subject areas.
- Facilitate the exchange of best practices within the RDM community and support knowledge transfer across NFDI consortia.
- Experiment with and evaluate various training formats.

Time Frame

The Hybrid Event took place between 28 October and 11 December 2025.

Overview of the Hybrid Format

The Hybrid Event combined the following training formats:

- A lunch-to-lunch in-person Kick-Off Event (approximately eight teaching hours);
- An online interactive workshop series (approximately 18 teaching hours);
- Self-learning modules (approximately 14 teaching hours);
- An asynchronous homework phase.

In addition, there was an evaluation consisting of surveys, expert and semi-structured interviews, and a focus group discussion.

2. Background and Initial Training Plan

2.1. Training Goals in the Project Proposal

In our initialisation phase proposal, we intended to set up and evaluate RDM training and assist consortia in creating training materials. These objectives remained unchanged, but the training formats did change. Initially, we stated that we would run a pilot one-month Online Workshop Series and a one-week Summer School involving a diverse group of participants from the four initial NFDI consortia. We selected these two prototype events because we considered them to be equally valuable, with different training durations and intensities designed to address the needs of various user groups. In addition, we also wanted to provide self-learning training materials to test an additional format.

2.2. Constraints and Adaptation During Implementation

As the initialisation phase of the project was only funded for one year, there was limited time to organise separate training events/formats. Our four initial use cases — BERD@NFDI, KonsortSWD, NFDI4Memory and NFDI4Microbiota — provided feedback on the initial plan and indicated a preference for shorter in-person events and a more spread-out schedule to accommodate our target audience of experienced professionals with personal obligations. We also wanted to create stronger continuity between training elements. Consequently, we decided to merge the formats into a single hybrid learning pathway rather than three separate activities. This approach was intended to lead to higher levels of participant engagement, stronger learning progression and the direct application of knowledge.

3. Pedagogical Concept and Design Principles

3.1. Learning Objectives

By the end of the Hybrid Event, participants were expected to:

- Explain core RDM concepts, infrastructures and networks.
- Develop data stewardship and change management skills.
- Design or adapt discipline-specific RDM training materials.
- Develop didactic skills and explain what motivates training participants.
- Reflect on organisational and cultural change in research practices.
- Familiarise themselves with and assess various training formats.

3.2. Target Audience

The target audience for the Hybrid Event was beginners and experienced professionals in RDM who currently deliver — or intend to deliver — generic and/or discipline-specific training. This included trainers, training coordinators, data stewards, RDM support staff and researchers involved in training activities.

3.3. Design Principles

The Hybrid Event was based on the following principles:

1. Progressive Learning Structure

Participants moved through the following stages: conceptual understanding, deepening knowledge, application to disciplinary context, and reflection and knowledge exchange.

2. Blended and Hybrid Learning

The Hybrid Event combined in-person interaction with synchronous online events, such as workshops, open hours for Q&A, and a wrap-up event, as well as asynchronous self-learning and homework.

3. Learning-By-Doing

Participants developed training materials during the Hybrid Event and some of them also taught workshops.

4. Community Building

The Hybrid Event encouraged exchanges and collaboration between different NFDI consortia and between participants with different levels of experience.

4. Structure of the Hybrid Training Event

4.1. Phase 1 — Kick-Off Event (In-Person)

The Kick-Off Event took place on 28 and 29 October 2025 at the ZB MED — Information Centre for Life Sciences in Cologne. Focusing on data stewardship and strategic change management in RDM, it included activities such as lectures, interactive sessions, group discussions and networking.

By the end of the Kick-Off Event, participants were expected to:

- Identify and manage their stakeholders.
- Clearly communicate their role and services to foster collaboration and adoption.
- Set meaningful strategic goals in collaboration with stakeholders and translate these into actionable plans.
- Prioritise daily responsibilities to free up time for strategic initiatives.
- Evaluate the impact of planned changes and manage change effectively.
- Build resilience in handling different responses to change.

The Kick-Off Event was intended to mark the start of the storyline and build a sense of community at the beginning of the event. Participants gained the strategic and conceptual context needed for the subsequent training phases and had the opportunity to network and get to know each other in person, which increased the likelihood of engagement in online activities. As the topic of this event — data stewardship and strategic change management — focused on soft skills, it was not related to later formats in terms of content. Therefore, participants who could not join in person would not be excluded.

4.2. Phase 2 — Online Workshop Series & Self-Learning Modules

The online interactive workshop series took place from 3 to 21 November 2025. There were six workshops in total, held every Tuesday and Thursday from 9am to 12pm. The specific topics covered were:

1. 4 November 2025: [Foundations of RDM for Beginners](#)
2. 6 November 2025: [Practical Data Protection in Research](#)
3. 11 November 2025: Python for Beginners ([Python Basics](#), [Introduction to Pandas](#))
4. 13 November 2025: Git for [Beginners](#) and [Advanced](#) (two parallel sessions)
5. 18 November 2025: [Introduction to Galaxy Training!](#)
6. 20 November 2025: [Didactics & Motivation](#)

To support the online interactive workshop series, we offered self-learning modules on the following topics:

- Foundations of RDM for Trainers

- Open Science
- Python for Advanced
- Git for Beginners (repeated, as requested by the use cases)
- Data Management Plans (DMPs) for Trainers
- Data Sharing & Publishing

The guide for the self-learning modules can be accessed [here](#).

The online interactive workshop series and self-learning modules were intended to deepen participants' knowledge, offering them the opportunity to expand their understanding of RDM and prepare to apply it to their own discipline and consortium's needs.

4.3. Phase 3 — Asynchronous Homework Phase

The asynchronous homework phase took place from 24 November to 5 December 2025. The objective was for participants to put into practice the concepts acquired during the workshops and self-learning modules, and to adapt RDM training materials to their specific discipline. The guide to the asynchronous homework phase can be found [here](#). Tasks included designing training modules, adapting slides, and creating discipline-specific examples.

The aim of this phase was to build on the knowledge gained in Phase 2 and transform participants from learners into contributors by giving them the chance to apply and share what they had learned.

4.4. Phase 4 — Wrap-Up Event

The wrap-up event took place on 11 December 2025. Participants presented their asynchronous homework results (i.e. their adapted training materials) and the organiser received feedback in the form of a focus group discussion. This feedback covered the entire Hybrid Event and provided an opportunity to share experiences, identify challenges, and collect ideas for future training programmes.

The wrap-up event aimed to foster community building and facilitate reflection and evaluation. It also closed the learning cycle and provided insight into project activities.

At the end of the hybrid event, participants received a certificate of attendance. This specified whether they had attended the Kick-Off event and which online workshops they had attended. Participation in the self-learning modules and other phases was not recorded on the certificate.

5. Evaluation Strategy

Following the Kick-Off Event and Online Workshop Series, we conducted a survey mainly to evaluate the training content and satisfaction levels. Following the 'Python for Beginners' workshop, we conducted an adapted survey from The Carpentries to gauge participants' subjective evaluations of their newly acquired skills, self-assurance, and knowledge.

Following the Self-Learning Modules, we conducted semi-structured interviews with two experts to evaluate the didactics and content of the modules.

To evaluate the Asynchronous Homework, we held a discussion with two participants.

To evaluate the event's overall effectiveness and satisfaction, we conducted semi-structured interviews with three participants to identify positive and negative learning experiences relating to the different training formats. We also conducted a focus group discussion.

The evaluation report of the Hybrid Event is available on Zenodo via the following DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18330262>.

6. The “Red Thread” of the Event

The Hybrid Event began with an in-person Kick-Off Event to establish a sense of community. Participants had the opportunity to get to know each other before engaging online. For this event, we selected the soft skill topic of 'Strategic Data Stewardship & Change Management' to appeal to participants of all levels.

We then ran the Online Workshop Series and Self-Learning Modules in parallel, enabling participants to deepen their RDM and training knowledge by selecting the training that best suited their interests, knowledge, skills and schedule.

Based on this, during the Asynchronous Homework Phase, we offered participants the opportunity to apply and adapt this knowledge to their own discipline within their consortium.

The Wrap-Up Event allowed participants to share results, reflect on the experience and evaluate the different formats of the Hybrid Event.

This progression ensured that participants understood RDM concepts, learnt training approaches and applied them to their discipline, reflecting collectively on the results in a community where they were welcome and included.

7. Lessons Learned and Outlook

The challenges included the tight timeframe of the project, identifying a suitable in-person format for our target audience, recruitment and finding reusable self-learning training materials. These challenges are discussed in detail in the Hybrid Event evaluation report (p. 15), which is available on Zenodo via the following DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18330262>.

We believe that hybrid training formats can efficiently combine different learning styles if they are clearly explained and what the learning goals of each format are. The materials must also be adapted to the format in question.

While it is difficult to quantify, we believe that starting with an in-person event encouraged participants to engage online subsequently, as they were eager to contribute their own experiences and questions during the online workshops. It would have been better to embed the self-learning modules between in-person events and give participants more time to complete them.

The homework phase was essential for disciplinary adaptation, but it could have been more effective if it had been announced at the beginning of the event and if participants had been given more time.

The evaluation results — the most important of which are to focus on onsite training and online workshops to foster social learning and motivation — will inform future RDM training initiatives within NFDI.

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